

EXTRACTION OF CHROMIUM FROM WASTEWATER

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Bakirov Begzod Tokhtaboy oglu

Gulistan State University

3rd year student of "Chemistry"

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It is known that from ancient times cattle breeding has been one of the main types of labor of our people. Livestock products are used not only as food, but also as clothing and entertainment products. Pet skins are used in the production of clothing. As a result of the leather processing stages, leather products are obtained for the production of clothing and footwear. Leather is obtained from the highest quality footwear products. There are such tanneries in all regions of the country. Peng Sheng LLC (Q / K) and Max Charm Export LLC (Q / K) are leather processing enterprises in the Syrdarya region.

Leather processing and leather production technology is carried out in 3 stages. In the first stage, in order to soften the skin, lime (CaCO_3 (MgCO_3)) is soaked in water, the skin softens. In the second stage, the skin is divided into 3 parts on the basis of special technologies. The upper layer of wool (from which it is used in the manufacture of pottery (tandoor)), the middle layer is processed to obtain leather, the inner layer of oil (for the preparation of food for fish). In the third stage of skin treatment, basic cleaning is carried out. The middle layer of the extracted skin is melted in special pools, and chromium III hydroxide is added. H_2SO_4 solution is then added to the solution. Once these steps are completed, a durable and strong raw product is formed.

After the completion of the first and third stages, CaCO_3 , MgCO_3 , $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$, CaSO_4 , MgSO_4 and other amorphous sediments remain in the solution. These waters are called effluents. Unfortunately, in many areas, these effluents are discharged into ditches or fields. Sulfates and carbonates that fall to the ground form complex sediments that are insoluble in water and acids. This, of course, leads to a sharp decline in land productivity.

Sewage is causing serious damage not only to productivity, but also to the environment. Carbonates, sulfates, ammonia in wastewater discharged into fresh air decompose as a result of sunlight and heat to form carbon dioxide, sulfur IV and VI oxides, ammonia. These, in turn, accumulate in the atmosphere and cause acid rain in the vicinity of the plant.

Wastewater also contains chromium (Cr) Rubidium (Rb) and other precious metals. For example, 23.5 kg of Cr (OH) ₃ is worth 25 million soums. The cost of 1 kg of chromium hydroxide is 1 million 60 thousand soums, and 1 gram - 10,600 soums. During the inspection of the wastewater of Peng Sheng and Max Charm Export tanneries, it was found that it contains 5 g / l and 8 g / l of chromium compounds.

Expensive and recyclable products, especially chromium extraction technologies, are slowly spreading throughout the country. This process is a 3-stage process that cleans not only metals but also microbes, trace elements and acids from wastewater.

First, the wastewater is passed through electrolytic baths. In this case, heavy and strong metals are attached to the cathode and fall out of the solution. After this stage, up to 80% of the chromium compounds are separated from the wastewater and used for recycling.

In the next stage, the wastewater is treated using sand ponds. At this stage, the macro-substances in the water: lime residues, wool and hair waste are separated from the solution by binding to the sand.

In the final stage, the wastewater is treated with Al (OH) ₃. Due to the viscous properties of Al (OH) ₃ on the surface, microelements, weak acids, microbes left in the wastewater are adsorbed.

Upon completion of these stages, the wastewater will be treated and used for irrigation.

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